

ACCUMULATION OF DAMAGE IN ALUMINUM MMCS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of reinforcement size and volume fraction on damage related to particle cracking and decohesion taking place during tensile straining has been studied using two dispersion reinforced aluminum matrix composite systems. Commercially pure (Al-1070) and aluminum-magnesium (Al-5050) matrices were reinforced with SiC particles of mean sizes 3, 10 and 30 μm in volume fractions of 10 and 20%.

The stiffness, related to damage, decreased with increasing strain. The damage term could be expressed in a power-law form and the overall rate of damage accumulation increased with reinforcement volume. The rate was higher for the quenched composites.

In general, a lower elongation to failure was associated with a higher damage accumulation rate. The lower ductility of those composites containing larger particles with the same reinforcement volume fraction, is regarded as a result of an increase in void accumulation rate. The void volume fraction was observed to accelerate with increasing tensile strain. A larger amount of void growth occurred in the lower volume fraction composites.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of particle reinforced metal matrix composites are controlled by the complex interaction between matrix and reinforcement. Thus, the predictions of any model need to be compared with the results from a composite system where the characteristics of the reinforcement are varied. In this case a study has been carried out on the influence of particle size and volume fraction on the evolution of damage in the form of particle cracking and decohesion during the tensile straining of two SiC particle-reinforced aluminum matrix composite systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

Commercially pure aluminum (Al-1070) and Al-1% Mg (Al-5050) powders were mixed with SiC particles of mean sizes 3, 10 and 30 μm in volume fractions of 10 and 20%. These were hot pressed just below the liquidus temperatures at 650°C and then extruded through a 50:1 extrusion ratio at 420°C. Heat treatments consisting of reheating to the extrusion temperature followed by a quench or by a slow cool to room temperature were carried out on machined pieces. After this, the gauge surface was polished to a 1 μm finish to remove any damage and show the extent and nature of surface deformation away from the fracture surface.

Tensile tests were carried out at a strain rate of $3.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The specimens had two strain

gauges attached. Strain, cross-head displacement and load were recorded continuously during each test. The stiffness was measured using an unloading and reloading method to remove the influence of local microyielding induced by residual thermal stresses. The elongation to failure was recorded for each composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial elastic modulus appeared to be relatively independent of particle size, but strongly dependent on the volume fraction of reinforcement. This result is in accordance with simple theories of load transfer and implies that all three size fractions of reinforcement had similar aspect ratio distributions. Quenching showed no consistent influence on the modulus.

On straining the composites in tension the stiffness decreased continuously with increasing strain, indicating that damage was being steadily accumulated. This increase in compliance was seen as an apparent decrease in the elastic modulus \bar{E} . When particle cracking or interface debonding occur during plastic deformation, the elastic modulus will decrease as a result. Figs. 1 and 2 show this effect and the elastic modulus appears to be a direct measure of the extent of damage to the reinforcement. Figs. 1 and 2 give the apparent modulus change in terms of damage, D , expressed by

$$D = 1 - \bar{E}/E \quad (1)$$

where \bar{E} is the apparent elastic modulus after a given strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ and E is the original or unstrained elastic modulus. Eqn. (1) is applicable for uniform deformation to a strain of ϵ_m . In order to compare all the data, a normalized strain $(\bar{\epsilon}/\epsilon_m)$ was employed. Using this approach all the damage occurring in the different composites could be expressed by

$$D = A (\bar{\epsilon}/\epsilon_m)^n \quad (2)$$

where A and n are constants for a given material. The constant A may be regarded as the damage coefficient and indicates the amount of damage at the end of the uniform deformation stage, i.e. when $\bar{\epsilon}$ equals ϵ_m . The exponent n is particularly significant since it indicates the rate at which damage is accumulated. Tables 1 and 2 give the A and n values for each composite. Also included is the elongation to failure (ϵ_f). In general the tensile ductility decreased with increase in damage accumulation exponent.

The rate of damage accumulation increased with increasing volume fraction and was generally greater for the quenched composites. Lloyd [1] has shown that if the damage parameter is considered as a function of the composite flow stress, the shape of the curve is consistent with the stress dependence of fractured particles. Consideration of the change in modulus with strain allows damage to be defined, which reflects the decrease in load carrying ability of the particles as they crack or decohere. However, the increase in D with strain was faster than indicated by the extent of particle cracking.

The tensile elongation is sensitive to heat treatment, decreasing with increasing strength and decreasing work hardening rate, so the matrix condition is very important in the fracture process. The stronger matrix of the quenched material displayed a higher damage accumulation rate and this effect was particularly more noticeable for the larger volume fraction reinforcements with large particles. Fracture initiates in the clusters of reinforcing particles. Owing to elastic misfit and the plastic constraint of the particles, the matrix between the particles is subjected to high triaxial stresses causing fracture of the matrix ligament to occur

between the particles.

In both metal matrix alloy systems tested, the tensile ductility decreased with increase in particle size and volume fraction. It is well documented [2,3,4] that particle reinforced metal matrix composites fail by a mechanism of ductile void growth and coalescence. The reduction in ductility seen with increasing particle fraction has two possible origins. First, the greater number of particles leads to a larger number of void nuclei and secondly, the greater volume fraction of reinforcement creates greater stress triaxiality between the particles and void growth may be faster. The reduced ductility with particle size is the consequence of an increased void nucleation rate. Additional reduction in ductility is seen on comparing Al-1070 with Al-5050 (and indeed further reduction in ductility if stronger matrices are used) and is the effect of matrix yield strength. Stronger matrices will result in greater particle stresses at the onset of flow. This results in a greater rate of void nucleation.

Mummery et al [5] using x-ray microtomography showed that void growth rate increased with increased volume fraction of reinforcement for 30 μm diameter particles in an Al-1070 matrix owing to increased stress triaxiality between the particles. Their data is replotted in Fig. 3. The true strain is normalized with the true strain to failure. This figure shows the increase in void volume fraction as a function of increasing strain for both composite materials, with a maximum void fraction of about 0.12 for the 5% reinforced material, and about 0.05 for the 20% particle reinforced composite.

The void volume fraction (V) may be expressed in the form:

$$V = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\bar{\epsilon}}{\epsilon_f} \right)^{\frac{1}{p+1}} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}$ is the strain and ϵ_f the strain to failure. The parameter p is a material constant and indicates the manner and rate of void accumulation. For the 5/30 composite, p was relatively low ($p = 30$) and the void volume fraction increased steadily with increasing strain, increasing towards failure, whereas p for the 20/30 composite was higher and somewhat variable ($p \sim 100$). The void fraction was very low initially, also increasing towards final failure.

The onset of void nucleation is the dominant process controlling the ductility in these materials. Void growth continues until a critical void size or volume fraction is attained. This is generally determined by some geometrical consideration. If the simplest formulation for ductile rupture is considered [6] voids coalesce by shear failure in the matrix between the voids when the plastic constraint for flow localization is removed. This occurs when the void height is equal to the intervoid spacing. This condition is satisfied owing to void nucleation on increasing the volume fraction of void nucleating sites to 0.16. Thus, for the high volume fractions of reinforcements found in commercial particle reinforced metal matrix composites the nucleation process is expected to dominate if void nucleation occurs at the reinforcing phase. It is, therefore important to isolate and identify the void nucleation process and to consider the influencing microstructural parameters.

Mummery, Derby and Scruby [7] monitored the acoustic emissions on tensile straining a series of SiC reinforced aluminum-matrix composites containing a systematic variation in the microstructural parameters. They showed that each acoustic emission corresponded to one nucleation event and found that there was void nucleation from the onset of plastic deformation and that continued throughout the plastic region involving some 10%-20% additional strain, indicating considerable void growth before failure. The number of emissions at a given far-field strain, increased with particle size and volume fraction, correlating with a decrease in

ductility, but were independent of matrix strength and heat treatment. At all reinforcement levels, these acoustic emission results [7] showed that the fraction of reinforcing particles, fractured or decohered, was independent of the total reinforcement volume fraction (i.e. at a given strain the fraction of failed particles was the same for all metal matrix composites of that matrix alloy and reinforcement size). Figs. 3 and 4 indicated that a larger degree of void growth occurred in the lower volume fraction material prior to failure. This is consistent with the void nucleation being associated with the reinforcing particles and hence the critical condition for coalescence occurring at lower strains for the more closely spaced voids in the higher volume fraction material.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The overall damage related to particle fracture and debonding in SiC particle reinforced aluminum alloys decelerated with increasing strain and may be expressed using a power-law equation. The overall rate of damage accumulation increased with reinforcement volume and was greater for the quenched composites with the stronger matrices.
2. In general, a greater elongation to failure was associated with a lower damage accumulation rate. The greater ductility of those composites with a smaller particle size for the same reinforcement volume is regarded as the consequence of a decrease in void accumulation rate.
3. The void volume fraction was observed to accelerate with increasing tensile strain. A larger amount of void growth occurred in the lower volume fraction composites.

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Table 1 Al-1070 matrix - Damage Data and Elongation

Composite - $V_f(\%)$ followed by particle size (μm)	Slowly Cooled			Quenched		
	A	n	$\epsilon_f, \%$	A	n	$\epsilon_f, \%$
10/10	0.086	0.15	20.8	0.064	0.16	20.1
10/30	0.88	0.28	19.7	0.059	0.15	19.1
20/3	-	-	18.5	0.131	0.51	17.0
20/10	0.117	0.41	18.3	-	-	16.8
20/30	0.142	0.41	12.5	0.084	0.53	9.5

Table 2 Al-5050 matrix - Damage Data and Elongation

Composite- $V_f(\%)$ followed by particle size (μm)	Slowly Cooled			Quenched		
	A	n	$\epsilon_f, \%$	A	n	$\epsilon_f, \%$
10/10	0.068	0.20	12.8	0.069	0.26	10.2
20/3	0.119	0.34	12.5	0.028	0.30	10.7
20/10	0.055	0.47	11.4	0.034	0.53	9.5
20/30	0.114	0.39	7.6	0.092	0.43	5.9

Figure 1. Damage (eqn. 1) accumulation with true strain for Al-1070 matrix composite. SC indicates slowly cooled, Q indicates quenched.

Figure 2. Damage (eqn. 1) accumulation with true strain for Al-5050 matrix composite, SC indicates slowly cooled, Q indicates quenched.

Figure 3. Void volume fraction vs. normalized true strain for Al-1070 matrix composite.